

Vuzix M4000

Recording Videos

WATERLINE

A white wavy line graphic is positioned below the text 'WATERLINE', consisting of two curved lines that create a sense of motion or a wave.

How to use Vuzix M4000 Camera Application

Without Voice commands

Taking a Picture

Open the Camera App

- Swipe on the touchpad to navigate to the camera app.
- Tap the centre of the touchpad to open it.

Take a Picture

- Once the camera app is open, tap the touchpad to take a picture.

Recording a Video

Open the Camera App

- **Swipe on the touchpad to find and open the camera app.**
- **Tap the touchpad to open it.**

Start Recording

- **Swipe forward or backward on the touchpad to select the recording mode.**
- **Tap the touchpad to start recording.**

Stop Recording

- **Tap the touchpad again to stop recording.**

Voice commands

Taking a Picture

Turn On the Device

- Make sure the Vuzix M4000 is turned on.

Activate the Camera

- Say “Open Camera” to activate the camera app.

Take a Picture

- Once the camera is open, say “Take Photo” to capture a picture.

Recording a Video

Activate the Camera

- Say “Open Camera” to start the camera app.

Start Recording

- Say “Start Recording” to begin video recording.

Stop Recording

- When you’re ready to stop recording, say “Stop Recording.”

